

TESOL AS FOREIGN EXPERIENCE AND A MODERN APPROACH TO LEARNING ENGLISH.

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***Abstract.** Being at the intersection of interscientific integration, the issue of innovative mechanisms and pedagogical approaches for the purposes of modernization, improving the quality of pedagogical competence and education in general is relevant.*

Uzbekistan has made a huge breakthrough in the educational sphere: foreign universities are opening on the territory of Uzbekistan, foreign teachers teach in private schools, students have the opportunity to undergo internships in their specialty in foreign countries.

With the strengthening and development of international relations, the issue of studying foreign languages, one of which is English, is relevant.

At the moment, one of the criteria for successful socialization on a global scale is fluency in English.

To reveal, understand the features and capabilities of modern pedagogy as a science, the role of which is not only in teaching, but also in the education of a person; first of all, when starting to modernize the professional competence of teachers, we should clearly set goals for what and what result we want to achieve by transforming the education system and updating it to modern realities.

American program TESOL (Teaching English for Speakers of Other Languages)- teaching English as a foreign language, or complete immersion in the language environment using and integrating the latest methods, pedagogical techniques, modern materials, thereby achieving the goal of removing the language barrier, free perception and proficiency in modern English, both oral and written, which entails high adaptability in the English-speaking environment.

Methodologies Desuggestopedia, Communicative Language Teaching, Total Physical Response in learning English as a foreign language, focuses on attention, memory and comprehension of the material being studied based on the mental, physiological, mental processes of each age group of the student and technology in the management of the educational process as Concept Checking Questions, Seating the Arrangement will allow effective interaction and feedback between the teacher and students.

***Keywords:** TESOL, desuggestopedia method, total physical response, communicative language teaching, Concept Checking Questions (CCQ), effective seating arrangement.*

***Аннотация.** Находясь на стыке межнаучных интеграций актуален вопрос об инновационных механизмах и педагогических подходах в целях модернизации, повышения качества педагогической компетентности и образования в целом.*

Узбекистан сделал огромный прорыв в образовательной сфере: открываются иностранные ВУЗы на территории Узбекистана, в частных школах преподают иностранные учителя, у студентов есть возможность проходить стажировку по специальности в зарубежных странах.

С усилением и развитием международных отношений актуален вопрос изучения иностранных языков, одним из которых является английский.

На данный момент одним из критериев успешной социализации в мировом масштабе является свободное владение английским языком.

Для раскрытия, осознания особенностей и возможностей современной педагогики как науки, роль которая не только в обучении, но и воспитание человека; прежде всего начиная модернизацию профессиональной компетентности учителей, следует четко проставить цели, для чего и какого результата мы хотим достигнуть, преобразовывая систему образования и актуализируя ее к современным реалиям.

Американская программа TESOL (Teaching English for Speakers of Other Languages) - обучение английскому как иностранного языка, или полное погружение в языковую среду используя и интегрируя новейшие методики, педагогические техники, современные материалы, тем самым достигая поставленной цели - снятия языкового барьера, свободное восприятие и владение современным английским языком как устным, так письменным видом речи, что влечет высокую адаптивность в англоязычной среде.

Методологии “Desuggestopedia”, “Communicative Language Teaching”, “Total Physical Response” в изучении английского как иностранного, фокусируется на внимание, памяти и осмысление изучаемого материала основываясь на психических, физиологических, ментальных процессах каждой возрастной группы учащегося, а техника в управление учебного процесса как “Concept Checking Questions” (CCQ), “Seating Arrangement” позволит эффективно взаимодействовать и обратной связи между педагогом и учениками.

Ключевые слова: *TESOL, метод Desuggestopedia, Total Physical Response, Communicative Language Teaching, Concept Checking Questions (CCQ), effective seating arrangement.*

Annotatsiya. *Fanlararo integratsiya chorrahasida joylashganligi sababli, pedagogic kompetensiya va umuman ta’lim sifatini modernizatsiya qilish, yaxshilash uchun innovatsion mexanizmlar va pedagogic yundashuvlar masalasi dolzarbdir.*

O‘zbekiston ta’lim sohasida ulkan yutuqni amalga oshirdi: O‘zbekiston hududida xorijiy universitetlar ochilmoqda, xorijlik o‘qituvchilar xususiy maktablarda dars bermoqda, talabalar o‘z mutaxassisliklari bo‘yicha xorijiy mamlakatlarda amaliyot o‘tash imkoniyatiga ega bo‘ldilar.

Xalqaro aloqalarning mustahkamlanishi va rivojlanishi bilan chet tillarini o‘rganish masalasi dolzarb bo‘lib, ulardan biri ingliz tilidir. Ayni paytda global miqyosda muvaffaqiyatli ijtimoiylashuv mezonlaridan biri bu ingliz tilini ravon bilishdir.

Zamonaviy pedagogikaning fan sifatidagi xususiyatlari va imkoniyatlarini ochib berish, uning o‘rni nafaqat o‘qitishda, balki shaxs tarbiyasida ham bo‘lishi; Avvalo, o‘qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyasini modernizatsiya qilishga kirishar ekanmiz, biz ta’lim tizimini o‘zgartirish va uni zamonaviy voqelikka yangilash orqali qanday va qanday natijaga erishmoqchi ekanligimizni aniq belgilab olishimiz kerak.

TESOL (Boshqa tillarda so‘zlashuvchilar uchun ingliz tilini o‘rgatish) Amerika dasturi - ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o‘rgatish yoki eng so‘nggi usullar, pedagogik texnikalar, zamonaviy materiallardan foydalangan holda va integratsiyalashgan til muhitiga to‘liq sho‘ng‘ish, shu bilan til to‘siqlarini bartaraf etish maqsadiga erishish, zamonaviy ingliz tilini og‘zaki va yozma ravishda

erkin idrok etish va bilish, bu ingliz tilida so'zlashuvchi muhitda yuqori moslashuvchanlikni talab qiladi.

"Desuggestopediya" metodologiyalari, Ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganishda "Kommunikativ til o'qitish", "Umumiy jismoniy javob" o'quvchining har bir yosh guruhining aqliy, fiziologik, mafkuraviy jarayonlari asosida o'rganilgan materialga e'tibor, xotira va tushunishga qaratilgan e'tibor, xotira va tushunishga qaratilgan bo'lib, ta'lim jarayonini boshqarishdagi "Tushunchalarni tekshirish savollari" (CCQ), "O'tirish tartibi" deb ta'lim jarayonini boshqarishdagi texnika o'qituvchi va talabalar o'rtasida samarali o'zaro ta'sir va fikr-mulohazalarni o'tkazish imkonini beradi.

***Kalit so'zlar:** TESOL, "Desuggestopedia" usuli, "Umumiy Jismoniy Javob", "Kommunikativ tilni o'rgatish", "Kontseptsiyani Tekshirish Savollari" (CCQ), O'tirishni samarali tartibga solish.*

Introduction. Nowadays, the tendency of globalization of commerce, education had influenced our life, so many people are trying to learn foreign languages to communicate effectively with each other. Some individuals learn a language faster than others or some can't speak even if they learned a language for a long time.

Every parent wants to give to their child the best things in life and one of them is education. Parents usually think the earlier the child starts studying a foreign language the faster the child can adapt to a harder competition's life, but the successful result of acquiring a language for young learners depends on effective methodologies and all of the country's education system.

The most important problem of education is the examination system of foreign languages. The goal of studying foreign language is passing and preparing for an exam. An ordinary teacher is usually the "explainer" and doesn't know how to teach naturally, with pleasure.

Strategies for integration of the four skills remove a rear of making mistakes, respect each person as a unique individual are the main teacher's target. Teacher have to remember about empathy, authenticity and respect.

Learning a foreign language means cultivation tolerance, studying the processes of cognitive perception, understanding the traditions, culture and characteristics of another people. Why some individuals learn a language faster or some can't speak even if they earned a language for a long time. How does it happen of why does it happen?

Teacher knows the subject matter very well, but has limited knowledge of methodology and this teacher was the explainer. Second, all lesson materials were not related to real life communication. Target of this method, what usually use in school is "Grammar translate method", that learns the language for only knowing this language but unfortunately not for communication. TESOL for children program learns about the concepts, "Teacher of Children" and "Children as Learners". Therefore, the object of this research will be the effective use and combination of desuggestopedia and communicative language teaching methods to build a lesson, taking into account the processes of cognitive thinking, verbal and logical memory of preschool children. The desuggestopedia method is the selection and adaptation of educational material on a variety of topics, taking into account the student's age, mnemonic processes, individual characteristics of types of perception and memory, as well as the opportunity to study the culture, history, art, traditions and many other aspects of social interaction of an English-speaking country. These methods mean to use only English language in the whole lesson.

Dessuggestopedia, this method has been developed to help students eliminate fear of studying foreign language and overcome the barriers to learning. The fear limited ability to succeed in learn, we may be using five to ten percent of our mental capacity instead of doing much better.

An interesting method is Total Physical Response, which is suitable not only for preschool children, but also for middle school students. This approach is necessary for the development of kinesthetic perceptions. Children learn information better when they directly interact with it, which is important for the child's mental and cognitive development. The name of the Communicative Language Teaching method speaks for itself and has recommended itself as effective in learning a foreign language, since the main goal and importance of the role of speech is primarily communicative. The main idea of this method being able to communicate required more than linguistic competence; it required communicative competence- knowing when and how to say what to whom. When constructing a lesson using several methods, it is important to take into account the organizational and meaningful process of the lesson. The organizational process includes proxemics, the space where learning will take place. Considering the number of students in the group, how and what distance should each student be placed depending on the type of activity being performed.

Effective seating arrangement means a suitable seating arrangement in the case of activities that will do in the class. A suitable seating arrangement can remove stress and make a pleasant atmosphere for studying. Each seating arrangements are effective only for one type of lesson activity, so it depends of the lesson activity. One seating arrangement would be more effective and fit to a chosen activity, but one arrangement would be ineffective. Therefore, when an activity for students will made, always need to think about a suitable seating arrangement.

If the activity needs team work, the effective seating arrangement in that case for young students 11 years of age would be "Modular of Groups" arrangement. In the class of 15 students' ages 10 years to 11 years of pre-intermediate level, activity is a teamwork activity, for this case need to choose "Modular or Groups" seating arrangement. 3 groups for 5 students in each group would be better for arrangement. It is good arrangement for teamwork activity. "Modular or Groups" seating arrangement are good for older students and for small discussion groups, but it is difficult to interact with the whole class for Students and a teacher. In that case Students will communicate in their own group and a teacher can't interact and control three groups at the same time. As an enabler teacher definitely need to choose this arrangement for teamwork activity because the authority of a teacher during a lesson makes Students-Students communication worse.

Lesson activity needs to involve each student or working in pairs, in that case the more suitable and effective arrangement would be a "Horseshoe" arrangement. It is good for an individual activity or pairs (only two students), and the communication between a teacher and Students are very good. The teacher can control the whole class at the same time, but the communication between Students and Students is less. The teacher can observe each of the students and have good eye contact between Teacher-Students, but a teacher had authority of the class. As a communication teacher's lesson will include an individual work and teamwork equally, and depends on the activity need to choose a suitable seating arrangement for students. Visual Materials: colorful posters, cards, books, magazines, photographs and toys should have a place in the classroom. The content process is a clear sequence of topics that will include the study and use of words on one topic, taking into account an equal load on listening, speaking, reading, writing and useful information about the country being studied in a game format.

Fantasy and imagination important for students

Young learners like to have a lot of imagination. Fantasy and imagination can help to motivate this process of learning and make the process more interesting. Young learners easily learn by games. The teacher needs to make a lot of interesting activity. However, fantasy and imagination need to be close to reality and Students experience. Teacher teaches not only a subject, but also teaches about life. So, the theme of subject needs to be useful in real life. For example; to show impolite behavior and untidiness of people in the lesson, the teacher can create an interesting character and demonstrate to the children. It motivates the students to involve in a learning process. Giving learning materials through games makes learning much easier and interesting for young students.

Also, developing students' fantasy and imagination is very important too. During the lesson a teacher must include activities such as making their own story, a tale, a song, a drawing. It can motivate students in the learning process, and involves the whole class in that process.

What are some important aspects of giving instructions effectively and in a student friendly way?

Being clear, simple, and as short as possible, in addition to accurate instructions are effective methods. Teachers have to plan how to present their instructions in a way that every student will understand. During the class a teacher must remember about the speed of the speech, volume, tone quality of voice (richness, mellowness), and how to articulate (clear pronounce and stress of each word.) The teacher should speak slowly with a loud voice to make sure every student hears the directions well. If the instruction is long, the teacher needs to divide it into parts, and wait until the students are paying attention to the teacher before explaining. Also, the student's or teacher's demonstration is important to explain the instructions. Depends on the activity the teacher needs to change their voice volume. For example, the voice volume during the instruction to the whole class would be different from teaching to smaller groups of 3 students. The teacher is an important visual aid in the class. Therefore, a smiling face, friendly voice, good eye contact with the students are aspects of giving instructions effectively, and in a student friendly way. The next step is to make sure that instructions were understood Concept Checking Questions (CCQ).

What is elicitation? Why is it important?

Instead of giving a fishing rod the foolish teacher would give fish to the students and those students will never catch the fish. It is very important how a teacher gives questions to students during the lesson. If a teacher will make the questions such as "Do you like summer?" There remains one student's answer, which is Yes or No.

Eliciting is an important technique to figure out what students already know by asking specific questions instead of giving answers. It would be much better if a teacher asks: What season do you like and why is it your favorite season? After those questions the answer of the students would be more interesting and can show the student's knowledge of the language. The use of these methods gives good results in mastering a foreign language, where the age and individual physical and psychological characteristics of the student must be taken into account. The results of the study and personal experience showed the effectiveness of the described methods in learning English as a foreign language. Complete immersion and the communicative method in the lesson allow you to make maximum use of the English language and think in this language. Total response physical allows children with a preference for tactile and kinesthetic perception to activate their memory and attention with the help of motor and tactile perceptions. From a modern teacher, time requires high qualifications, knowledge not only of his subject, but also of methods, techniques, and the

ability to convey his knowledge in a professional and creative approach to planning a lesson and its content, taking into account the psychological and physiological characteristics of students that are also important for pedagogy.

Teacher need to be confident, but improve teaching skills, and work every day not only on making lesson plans. Also work on voice, gestures, face emotions, giving positive and constructive feedback, patience, and observation, improve classroom management techniques. Children are very sensitive; they sharply react on critical words, smiling, positive feedback, face emotions, gestures and a voice. Children can be soft clay and the teacher can sculpt everything. Therefore, the teacher must be responsible for them who believe in you and trust you a soul.

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